

ZAPS- Zone-averaged Accelerated Pebble-bed Simulator

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ABSTRACT

This work presents ZAPS (**Z**one-averaged **A**ccelerated **P**ebble-bed **S**imulator), a fast and flexible Monte Carlo tool for pebble-bed reactor analysis. Built on the widely used Serpent2 transport code and implemented through the modular Cerberus Python interface, ZAPS couples explicit Monte Carlo physics with an efficient zone-based treatment of pebble motion and fuel depletion. The framework's originality lies in its dual-loop architecture: an outer transport loop that updates flux distributions, and an inner recirculation loop that simulates pebble movement and burnup under a fixed flux. This strategy drastically reduces the number of costly transport calculations, enabling equilibrium-state determination within only a few hours on a standard workstation. When benchmarked against the reference Hyper-Fidelity framework (HxF) providing pebble-resolved data, using the generic fluoride-salt-cooled high-temperature reactor (gFHR) model, ZAPS reproduces average isotopic compositions and discharge burnup with excellent agreement while achieving over an order of magnitude reduction in runtime—up to 100× less CPU time to reach equilibrium. These results demonstrate that ZAPS currently provides one of the fastest pebble bed reactor simulation capabilities available, supporting detailed parametric studies and advanced applications such as fuel-cycle investigation and optimization.

Keywords: Monte-Carlo, Zone Simulator, Pebble Bed Reactor, Acceleration

1. INTRODUCTION

Pebble-bed reactor (PBR) simulation represents a critical step toward the deployment and optimization of advanced reactor concepts. The detailed modeling of these systems, however, remains challenging due to their intrinsic coupling between neutron transport, pebble motion, and fuel depletion. The strong spatial and temporal heterogeneities within the core due to the multi-pass behavior require explicit geometry descriptions and dynamic tracking of fuel elements, which lead to high computational demands and long simulation times when performed with Monte Carlo methods.

To address these challenges, the HxF (Hyper-fidelity) framework was developed to perform pebble-resolved simulations of transport, burnup, and motion in an integrated fashion based on the integration of Serpent2 [1] within the Python wrapper Cerberus [2]. HxF provides highly detailed insight into the neutronic and isotopic evolution of the reactor by explicitly modeling each pebble throughout the full core. It includes the handling of the pebble reinsertion and discard, based on a user-defined threshold. While this approach enables precise analysis of fuel behavior and core equilibrium states, providing the distribution of irradiation histories, its computational cost remains prohibitive for large-scale or parametric studies, requiring extensive high-performance computing resources.

Building upon the experience gained with HxF, a new simulation framework—named ZAPS (**Z**one-averaged **A**ccelerated **P**ebble-bed **S**imulator)—is developed to significantly reduce the computational

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burden of Monte Carlo equilibrium calculations. The core idea of ZAPS is to apply a dual-loop architecture that separates transport and depletion/motion computation. An outer loop updates the neutron flux distribution using the Monte Carlo transport code Serpent2 [1] and an explicit geometry representation (including core, pebble, and TRISO geometry), while an inner loop performs pebble recirculation and burnup calculations under a fixed flux. This structure drastically limits the number of costly transport evaluations required to reach the reactor's equilibrium state, thereby achieving a substantial speedup compared to tightly coupled pebble-wise simulations.

Additional features, such as accuracy refinement based on neutron population increase and motion time step reduction, are presented and discussed regarding solver resolution and computational time. The performance and accuracy of ZAPS are assessed through a detailed comparison with the reference HxF framework using the generic Fluoride-salt-cooled High-temperature Reactor (gFHR) model. The comparison focuses on equilibrium quantities such as the effective multiplication factor, discharged burnup, and isotopic distributions.

2. METHOD

2.1. ZAPS simulation tool

This section presents the ZAPS framework. The framework simulates the evolution of fuel composition in a pebble-bed reactor by explicitly representing individual pebbles for transport steps while grouping them into spatial zones to perform depletion steps efficiently. ZAPS operates on a "static" Serpent2 reactor model that includes a full geometric description of pebbles and TRISO particles, enabling high-fidelity Monte Carlo transport calculations. The workflow is implemented through the modular Cerberus Python interface, which orchestrates the dual-loop process, sequentially launching the transport step and directing the burnup and motion calculations. The user defines a set of parameters specifying the zone boundaries, neutron population size, motion time step, and overall convergence criteria. These parameters are detailed for the specific study case in the next section. The operating principles of the two loops are described below.

In the outer loop, ZAPS calculates the neutron flux across the explicit and static reactor geometry. The resulting flux is spatially averaged over the zones containing pebbles and passed to the depletion module, which performs the burnup calculations, named activation steps since the flux is not updated. The outer loop terminates once the relative difference in a user-defined convergence metric is achieved. For pebble-bed reactor (PBR) equilibrium searches, convergence is typically assessed based on the stabilization of the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}), which terminates the overall simulation.

In the inner loop, the previously averaged neutron flux in each zone is kept constant and used to alternate between pebble motion and depletion steps executed with Serpent2, leveraging its activation calculation capabilities. Cerberus handles the pebble motion dynamically between these steps. By maintaining a fixed flux during the inner iterations, the framework drastically reduces the number of costly transport calculations required to reach equilibrium while accurately capturing the isotopic evolution of the fuel. Pebble motion is modeled as a purely axial material transfer between zones: as pebbles move through the core, discharged pebbles from one end are reinserted at the other end with a random radial position drawn from the available radial zones to mimic the operational random reinsertion. Pebble discard can be triggered according to several user-defined criteria, such as the number of passes, accumulated burnup, or specific isotopic concentrations. The inner loop converges when the difference in discarded pebble burnup between two successive iterations falls below the specified tolerance. The resulting updated snapshot of isotopic compositions is then passed to the outer loop for a new transport calculation, providing a flux update for the next activation steps.

At full convergence, ZAPS provides a detailed description of the reactor's equilibrium state, including the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}), zone-averaged neutron flux and power distribution, burnup,

and isotopic maps. The overall detection capabilities and flexibility of Serpent offer the possibility to implement user-defined output metrics. It also provides valuable information on the discarded pebble population, such as the average burnup and isotopic composition. The overall workflow of the ZAPS simulation framework is illustrated in Figure 1, highlighting the dual-loop structure.

Figure 1. Workflow summary of the ZAPS simulation framework.

In addition, the overall structure of the framework allows the user to define specific convergence criteria and control the level of accuracy by increasing the number of simulated neutrons or by reducing the burnup/motion time step. In addition, the PBR configuration is entirely determined by the provided Serpent input file, offering broad applicability of ZAPS to both gas-cooled and salt-cooled PBR concepts. This aspect can also be extended to PBR concepts containing different types of pebbles, such as a mix of graphite and fuel pebbles. However, the current implementation is particularly suited to simple geometries, such as purely cylindrical cores, where zone construction remains straightforward. The motion scheme currently assumes purely axial motion, neglecting any radial pebble velocity profile. This limits the present applicability of the code to reactors with more complex geometries, such as conical regions or defueling/fueling chutes. Nevertheless, the strength of the framework lies in its dual-loop architecture, and future developments may extend its capabilities to more complex geometries, including user-defined radial transfer rates and advanced zone construction algorithms.

2.2. Study case

To evaluate and compare the performance of the developed simulation tool, the gFHR model is implemented within ZAPS. The reactor model -developed for neutronic benchmarks by Kairos Power- features a cylindrical core packed with pebbles of 2 cm radius. The pebble bed region is surrounded by a 60 cm-thick graphite reflector. Key geometric and fuel design parameters are summarized in Table I, and the explicit geometry implemented in Serpent is shown in Figure 2. The pebble positions for the static configuration are provided based on an FCC lattice structure, where the lattice parameter is selected to reach a core packing fraction of 60 %.

A specific feature of the gFHR design lies in the pebble geometry, where the TRISO particles are embedded in a graphite matrix located between radii 1.38 cm and 1.8 cm of the pebble, as shown in Figure 2. Each pebble contains 9022 TRISO particles, corresponding to a matrix packing fraction of 22 %.

Serpent2 uses ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data libraries [3], with material temperatures set to 900 K, corresponding to the nominal operating temperature of the reactor [4].

Figure 2. Serpent model of the gFHR, pebble, and TRISO particles.

Table I. Detailed characteristics of the gFHR, pebble, and TRISO particles

Core (cylinder)	
Total power	280 MWth
Number of pebbles	250 190
Pebbles	
Lattice structure	FCC (a=2.98 cm)
Layers radius (cm)	1.38, 1.8, 2
TRISO Particles	
Lattice structure	dispersed
Layers radius (μm)	212.5, 312.5, 352.5, 387.5, 427.5
Fuel form	UCO
Enrichment	19.55 wt%

2.3. Simulator parameters

The ZAPS framework requires a set of user-defined parameters controlling transport calculations, motion and depletion steps, and convergence criteria. The main simulation settings for the ZAPS workflow are summarized in Table II. The framework distinguishes between the outer-loop transport calculations and the inner-loop pebble motion and depletion steps, each governed by explicit convergence tolerances. Additional numerical parameters, such as the number of spatial zones and the number of subdivisions per zone, are also specified by the user. In the present reference case, the chosen zoning configuration results in a total of 256 groups of pebbles, corresponding to eight subdivisions within each of the 32 spatial regions. The subdivision indexes are assigned based on the number of accumulated passes and randomly attributed at the beginning of the simulation.

Table II. Simulation parameters used for the reference gFHR case.

Core zoning	
Axial \times radial zones	8 \times 4
Subdivisions per zone	8
Pebble discharge	
Pass threshold	8 passes
Residence time	522 days
Transport parameters (outer loop)	
Neutrons per cycle	2500
Number of cycles	10 (inactive), 100 (active)
Neutron multiplier	1.5
Convergence on k_{eff}	$\Delta k_{\text{eff}} \leq 100$ pcm
Motion and burnup parameters (inner loop)	
Time step	8.2 days
Time-step multiplier	0.9
Convergence on burnup	Δ discharge burnup $< 1 \times 10^{-3}$ %

In addition, ZAPS implements a neutron population multiplier and a time-step multiplier, which are applied respectively to the neutron population size and depletion time step at each outer-loop iteration. These features enhance numerical accuracy and contribute to convergence stability throughout the calculation.

Regarding convergence assessment, the objective of this work is to demonstrate the ability of ZAPS to determine the reactor's equilibrium composition starting from a fully fresh-fuel core. The calculation involves repeated pebble circulation, discard, and reinsertion of fresh fuel until an equilibrium state is achieved. The pebble discard is based on the number of accumulated passes, in this case set to a maximum of eight passes, corresponding to a residence time of 522 days. The script termination or convergence of the outer loop is thus justified by the stabilization of the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}). The results of this equilibrium calculation are compared against a reference HxF gFHR simulation for validation.

2.4. HxF dataset generation

To generate a reference dataset for comparison, an equilibrium simulation is also performed using the HxF framework. The HxF model relies on the same Monte Carlo transport code, Serpent2, and employs an identical gFHR core geometry, as illustrated in Figure 2. The simulation begins with a completely fresh fuel inventory and iteratively proceeds until an equilibrium core condition is achieved, defined by a stable neutron multiplication factor over one pass recirculations (62 days). The tool treats the pebble individually and solves transport after each motion/burnup depletion, resulting in a simple loop framework.

Each transport calculation in HxF employs 5×10^7 active neutrons and 5×10^6 inactive neutrons to ensure high statistical precision. The resulting relative uncertainties are approximately 1.1 % for pebble-wise neutron flux and 2.8 % for pebble-wise power, while the uncertainty in the multiplication factor remains below 30 pcm. Pebble motion is modeled with a time step of 3.8 days, and the discharge threshold is defined by a maximum of eight passes, yielding a residence time consistent with the reference ZAPS configuration.

All simulations are conducted at nominal operating temperatures using the same nuclear data library as in ZAPS to ensure consistent cross-section treatment. Additional details on the gFHR HxF simulation and the equilibrium determination methodology can be found in Reference [2].

3. RESULTS

3.1. Case convergence

The reference case defined in Table II is executed, and the evolution of the multiplication factor and discharged burnup throughout the calculation is shown in Figure 3. The figure combines the variation of the discharged burnup during the inner burnup/motion iterations with the corresponding k_{eff} values obtained at each outer transport iteration.

As shown, the simulation converges after six outer iterations, corresponding to six Monte Carlo transport calculations. In total, 400 burnup/motion steps are performed. For reference, 69 inner iterations follow the first transport calculation, while subsequent transport steps are followed by 86, 88, 108, and finally 40 inner iterations, respectively. Considering the multiplying factors defined in Table II, the neutron population has been multiplied by five in the last transport calculation, while the motion time step is reduced up to 5.3 days to enhance accuracy

At the beginning of the simulation, the first transport calculation is performed for a fully fresh-fuel core, producing the initial k_{eff} of 1.35. A total of 64 motion steps is then required to fully circulate the fresh fuel through the core (corresponding to 522 days with an 8.2-day time step). This explains the high number

of inner iterations observed in the first cycle (69 iterations) as the system stabilizes toward a consistent discharged burnup after the entire inventory circulation and discard. In subsequent cycles, the time-step multiplier progressively refines both pebble motion and burnup time step, which increases the number of steps required for inner-loop convergence. However, the final outer iteration requires fewer steps since the system is already near equilibrium, both in terms of discharged burnup and neutron multiplication factor (see Figure 3).

Finally, the statistical uncertainty in the multiplication factor decreases from 187 pcm in the initial transport calculation to 90 pcm in the final iteration, owing to the neutron population multiplier described in Table II.

Figure 3. Evolution of the multiplication factor and discharged burnup over the iterations.

3.2. Comparison with HxF

The comparison with HxF is first performed on the basis of the multiplication factor. The ZAPS-converged k_{eff} is 1.01313 ± 93 pcm, while the HxF equilibrium calculation yields 1.01494 ± 20 pcm, resulting in a difference of approximately 180 pcm. Additional comparisons are made using the discharged fuel burnup and the equilibrium power distribution.

Since ZAPS groups pebbles within zones and discards them based on their number of passes, it does not directly provide pebble-wise burnup data. However, the discharged burnup can be retrieved both as an overall average value and as a function of the radial zone index, as shown in Figure 4.

The average discharged burnup obtained with ZAPS differs by only 0.25 MW/kgHM from the HxF average value. Among the four radial zones in ZAPS, most of the deviation -compared to HxF- originates from the central ring ($r \in [0, 0.6$ m]) and the outer ring ($r \in [1.04, 1.2$ m]).

Similarly, Figure 5 compares the equilibrium, zone-averaged power density distributions between HxF and ZAPS. The relative differences between the two frameworks remain within the statistical uncertainty of the Serpent calculations (below ± 4 %). ZAPS slightly underestimates the power density near the bottom of the core, where HxF captures the localized effect of freshly inserted pebbles adjacent to the reflector. This discrepancy arises because ZAPS employs the zone homogenization over the lower axial region. A finer axial zoning could mitigate this effect.

Conversely, in the upper outer part of the core, ZAPS overestimates the power density. This stems from its limited ability to resolve the thin annular region of pebbles adjacent to the radial reflector that experience high thermal flux and significant local burnup. This behavior is consistent with the

Figure 4. Distribution and average values of discharged pebble burnup.

Figure 5. Equilibrium in-core power density for HxF (left), ZAPS (center), and relative difference (right).

previously noted burnup approximation effects in the outer radial zones.

An additional element of comparison is the isotopic composition of the discarded pebbles. The main isotopes of interest are considered and presented in Table III, along with the average and standard deviation values of atomic densities and the corresponding ZAPS calculated values.

Table III. Isotopic atomic densities (at/cm³).

Nuclide	HxF (mean)	HxF (std)	ZAPS
U-235	1.003×10^{21}	5.778×10^{19}	1.002×10^{21}
Pu-239	2.856×10^{20}	3.604×10^{19}	2.849×10^{20}
Cs-137	2.620×10^{20}	7.453×10^{18}	2.628×10^{20}
I-131	1.665×10^{18}	4.896×10^{17}	1.665×10^{18}
Sr-90	1.918×10^{20}	3.603×10^{18}	1.920×10^{20}
Xe-135	2.973×10^{16}	3.894×10^{15}	3.056×10^{16}
Kr-85	1.195×10^{19}	2.256×10^{17}	1.197×10^{19}

Most of the isotope density predictions obtained with ZAPS show negligible deviation from HxF average results. The isotope exhibiting the largest discrepancy is Xe-135, with a deviation of 2.7%. This difference is primarily attributed to the absence of decay or off-core cooling time in the ZAPS simulations, as isotopic concentrations are extracted immediately after the last activation or depletion step, resulting in a really low atomic density. For all other isotopes, the observed deviations remain below 0.2%, confirming the excellent capability of ZAPS in reproducing the average pebble behavior predicted by HxF.

Additional comparisons include the neutron energy spectrum and zone-averaged fast and thermal fluxes. Across all these metrics, the relative error remains below 5%, further supporting the robustness of ZAPS in capturing the zone-average neutronic behavior of the gFHR. The main limitation of the zone-averaged approach lies in its inability to fully resolve outlier behavior such as localized power peaking. In some regions—particularly at the bottom of the core where freshly inserted pebbles interact with the reflector—the local pebble power may differ from the zone-averaged value by up to 100%. While this does not significantly affect global neutronic quantities, it could impact future multiphysics applications where temperature and thus TRISO fuel performance are strongly influenced by power heterogeneities.

3.3. Computational performance

The dual-loop framework developed in ZAPS directly addresses the prohibitive computational cost of HxF, which requires extensive high-performance computing resources to tightly couple transport, burnup, and motion. By reducing the number of unique materials to 256 (as specified in Table II), ZAPS drastically lowers the memory footprint to approximately 5 GB, compared to the 400 GB required by HxF for the gFHR. Regarding transport, the loose coupling, resulting in five transport steps, demonstrates a much smaller computational allocation; ZAPS achieves equilibrium in only 18 CPU hours, while HxF requires about 5700 CPU hours for the same task. This reduction—over two orders of magnitude in total computational cost—illustrates the effectiveness of the dual-loop design, which minimizes the number of Monte Carlo transport evaluations while maintaining high accuracy. The resulting framework enables routine parametric and sensitivity studies on a single workstation, which were previously impractical using HxF.

4. CONCLUSION

This work introduced ZAPS, a fast and flexible Monte Carlo simulator for pebble-bed reactors. Built upon the Serpent2 transport code and implemented via the modular Cerberus interface, ZAPS couples detailed Monte Carlo physics with a zone-averaged treatment of pebble motion and burnup. The tool employs a dual-loop iterative scheme that drastically reduces the number of transport calculations required to reach equilibrium. Benchmarking against the HxF framework using the gFHR model demonstrates excellent agreement in all key neutronic parameters, including multiplication factor, isotopic inventories, and discharged burnup. The framework achieves more than a 300-fold improvement in computational efficiency while maintaining full compatibility with Serpent's geometry and physics capabilities. These results confirm that ZAPS offers one of the fastest and most accurate Monte Carlo equilibrium search tools currently available. Its modular structure facilitates a future integration with thermal-hydraulic, fuel performance, making it a valuable platform for future multiphysics and design studies. Ongoing developments focus on extending zone construction to non-cylindrical cores, incorporating user-defined radial transfer rates to mimic the pebble radial velocity profile. In summary, ZAPS bridges the gap between detailed pebble-resolved Monte Carlo modeling and practical reactor-scale equilibrium analysis, providing a powerful and efficient tool for next-generation pebble-bed reactor design.

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